

Estimation of acute and chronic aquatic toxicity for palmitic acid

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INTRODUCTION

This report documents the QSAR estimation of the Acute and chronic aquatic toxicity for palmitic acid by using theusing ECOSAR v2.0 software. All predictions conducted by ECOSAR (except for surfactants and dyes) are based on Log K_{ow} .

Palmitic acid is assigned within the neutral organics class. The QSARs for estimating the toxicity of neutral organics are traditional regressions developed from experimental toxicity values and Log K_{ow} values calculated with KOWWIN from EpiSuite v4.11.

As discussed in ECOSAR Methodology Document v2.0, the mode of action for non-reactive, neutral organic chemicals is narcosis (“baseline toxicity”). Some chemical classes have a more specific mode of toxic action. These are typically organics that are reactive and/or ionizable and exhibit excess toxicity in addition to narcosis. For these chemicals, toxicity is also correlated to their log K_{ow} values. Data show that the amount of excess toxicity to one or more organisms will generally decrease with increasing log K_{ow} values (decreasing solubility). This means that chemicals tend to act more like neutral organics (via narcosis) at higher log K_{ow} values.

Related to ECOSAR predicted effect levels, there is a maximum log K_{ow} cut-off for each class (“Max. log K_{ow} ”). Above the log K_{ow} cut-off values, the decreased solubility of the chemicals (i.e. hydrophobicity of molecule) will not likely result in toxicity to the organism for the given duration (48 to 96-hour test). This is reported by ECOSAR v2.0 as “No Effects at Saturation”.

Log K_{ow} cut-offs are 5 for daphnid acute endpoints and 6.4 for green algae 96-hour EC_{50} endpoints. For chronic exposures, the applicable log K_{ow} range is extended up to 8.0. The difference in log K_{ow} cutoffs between acute and chronic tests is expected as the hydrophobic nature of a test substance might not allow equilibrium to be achieved within the standard exposure durations for acute tests but may ultimately be achieved during chronic studies.

In addition to the log K_{ow} limits, water solubility is an important determinant of the toxicity of a chemical, especially for solids. Assuming that the K_{ow} is constant, the higher the melting point of a neutral organic chemical, the lower its water solubility. The water solubility of a chemical should be compared with the predicted toxicity value derived for a chemical. If the toxicity value is significantly greater than the measured or predicted maximum water solubility, then an effect is not expected to occur in a saturated solution. To check this, water solubility and melting point values are obtained from calculation by EpiSuite v4.11.

The following information on chemical identity were entered into the software:

Name: palmitic acid

IUPAC name: hexadecanoic acid

CAS Number: 57-10-3

SMILES : CCCCCCCCCCCCCCCC(=O)O

Molecular formula: C16 H32 O2

Molecular weight: 256.42

RESULTS

The toxicity values for palmitic acid derived from predicted log K_{ow} = 6.96 (KOWWIN from EpiSuite v4.11) are shown in Table 1. Additionally, water solubility was predicted to be 0.053 mg/L (WSKOWWIN from EpiSuite v4.11) while melting point was 61.8 °C (MPBPWIN).

Table 1 Aquatic toxicity predictions for palmitic acid (based on log K_{ow} pred = 6.96)

Endpoint	ECOSAR prediction [mg/L]	Alerts from ECOSAR
<i>Aquatic toxicity</i>		
<i>Daphnia</i> acute toxicity	0.066 (48 h-EC ₅₀)	Chemical may be not soluble enough to measure this predicted effect. Typically effect is not expected to occur in a saturated solution. Log K _{ow} greater than the endpoint specific cut-off value. No effect at saturation expected.
Algae toxicity	0.327 (96 h-EC ₅₀)	Chemical may be not soluble enough to measure this predicted effect. Typically effect is not expected to occur in a saturated solution. Log K _{ow} greater than the endpoint specific cut-off value. No effect at saturation expected.
<i>Daphnia</i> Chronic toxicity	0.023 (ChV)	Chemical may be not soluble enough to measure this predicted effect. Typically effect is not expected to occur in a saturated solution. Log K _{ow} greater than the endpoint specific cut-off value. No effect at saturation expected.
	0.016 (NOEC = ChV / √2)	
Algae toxicity	0.238 (ChV)	Chemical may be not soluble enough to measure this predicted effect. Typically effect is not expected to occur in a saturated solution. Log K _{ow} greater than the endpoint specific cut-off value. No effect at saturation expected.
	0.168 (NOEC = ChV / √2)	

The above results seem to indicate that palmitic acid is not toxic to aquatic organisms up to the limit of its water solubility predicted.

Additionally, the Log K_{ow} predicted and the decreased solubility of the chemicals (i.e. hydrophobicity of molecule) seems to indicate as well that it will not likely result in toxicity to *Daphnia* and algae.

Such results are consistent with the data available from the ECHA database where no acute neither chronic effect was identified within water solubility in the REACH dossier of Palmitic acid.

REFERENCES

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